

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Relations of Infinite Spaces in Full Voids and Constitution of Total Energies and their Effect on Matter

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ABSTRACT

I did this work and specifically this project to make a simple argument to show. There is something else behind the light; is new speed input has Energy and bring out a new relationship of light; and this new relationship will Change all the old settings that exists; and has an approach and my Project will improve the approach by providing the needs of physics. and has a consequence Positive total return and hence global performance level Physical and especially in the Field of the speed of light.

Key words: Fundamental relationship, universe, full space, stable relationship, speed of light

INTRODUCTION

I have introduced into these new concepts concerning the mathematical development; of full voids in infinite Spaces; and consequently. I have brought out a new concept is energy of infinite space; and speed and connecting them with the speed of light and energy. The concept is to better understand the notion of energy; constituting the voids of infinite spaces in my theorem. I try to result the Concept.

DISCUSSION

Hence, here is my statement for the proposal with graphics in the page as follows:^[1-5]

It was a complete theorem of the fundamental relationship of the following universe:

$$] A [=] 1 [;$$

The new benchmark based on 1 is as follows:

$$A=1;$$

General stable relationship (universal equilibrium relationship).

It was as a result of the mark:

$$A=B*C*D/Z^2$$

Hence, we have $B*C*D/Z^2=1'$;

And:

$$A=1;$$

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The question is what is $B*C*D/Z^2=A=1\neq 1'$?

Mathematics can be a physical side that ensures this relationship as follows:

$$A=E; \text{ and } 1'=C';$$

It was as you know:

$$E=B*C*D/Z^2;$$

Emphasis $B*D=M$;

The relationship becomes:

$$E=M*C/Z^2$$

It was as a result:

$$C/Z^2=C'=1'; Z=\text{square root } (C/C')=1';$$

Hence, we have: $E/M=C'$;

Consequence:

$$E=C'M;$$

Equation represents the interaction between energy and mass;

Moreover, this is the fundamental relationship of the universe.

Alternatively, we have:

$$E=1'=C'M;$$

$$1'=C'M \text{ equivalence } 1'/C' = M;$$

$$1'/C'=1;$$

Consequence of this relationship was always:

$$1=1';$$

Hence, the end result of this equation is the interval:

$$] E, M [$$

$$] 1, 1' [$$

Relationship of absolute gaps in the full space was:

$$E=M \text{ result was the result } E'=M'$$

Hence, we can solve the following range:

$$] 1^e, 1^{e'}, 1^m, 1^{m'} [$$

The equations needed for this range are as follows:

$$1^{E'} * 1^{M'} = 1^{E'M'}$$

$$1^{E'} * 1^M = 1^{EM}$$

$$1^{E'} * 1^{M'} - 1^{E'M'} = 0$$

$$1^{E'} * 1^M - 1^{EM} = 0$$

1 and 2 are equal, so we will write:

$$(1^{E'} * 1^M) - 1^{EM} = (1^{E'} * 1^{M'}) - 1^{E'M'}$$

$$(1^{E'} * 1^M) - (1^{E'} * 1^{M'}) = 1^{EM} - 1^{E'M'}$$

$$1^E (1^{E'} * 1^M - 1^{E'} * 1^{M'}) = 1^E (1^{EM} - 1^{E'M'})$$

$$1^E * (1^{E'} * 1^M) - 1^E * (1^{E'} * 1^{M'}) = 1^{EM} * 1^E - 1^{E'M'} * 1^E$$

$$1^{2E} * 1^M - 1^{2E} * 1^{M'} = 1^{2EM} - 1^{2E'M'}$$

$$1^{2E} * 1^M - 1^{2EM} = 1^E * 1^{E'} * 1^M - 1^E * 1^{E'} * 1^{M'}$$

$$1^{2E} (1^M - 1^{M'}) = 1^E * 1^{E'} (1^M - 1^{M'})$$

$$1^{2E} / (1^E * 1^{E'}) = (1^M - 1^{M'}) / (1^M - 1^{M'})$$

$$1^{2E} / (1^E * 1^{E'}) = 0^2 / 0$$

Hence, the end result is:

$$1^E / 1^{E'} = 0^+$$

$$1^E / 1^{E'} = 0^+ / 0 = 0^+$$

Hence, the great result is:

$$1^E / 1^{E'} = 0^+ / 0;$$

0 should, therefore, be another new equation, and the equation is:

$$0 = 1^{E'} * 0^2 / 1^E$$

It was in the calculation

$$1 = 1 + 0 = (1^{E'} * 0^2 / 1^E) + 1;$$

Calculation results of this research are:

$$N = N((1^{E'} * 0^2 + 1^E) / 1^E);$$

According the reference:

$$B * D = M;$$

$$\text{And: } C = C';$$

$$\text{So: } EZ^2 = C'M;$$

$$\text{That is: } Z^2 = C'M/E$$

Hence, the new theorem is as follows:

$$Z = \text{square root } ((C' * M) / E);$$

Alternatively, there is the following relationship:

$$C/C' = Z^2;$$

And:

$$Z = C'M/E$$

So:

$$C/C' = C'M/E;$$

So:

$$C^2 M/E = C;$$

Hence, the new speed of light is:

$$(C')^2 = EC/M;$$

Final result is:

$$C' = \text{square root } ((E * C) / M)$$

This relationship explains the massive energy in the new speed of light C'.

The parameters of the relationship are as follows:

E: Energy of particles found in space

C: The former speed of light which is known to everybody

C': The new speed of light is C' > C

M: Mass of particles found in an estimated time

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